

METHOD OF QUALIFICATION OF NUCLEAR AND ENVIRONMENTAL SAFETY SYSTEMS OF NUCLEAR POWER PLANTS WITH VVER-1000 AND AR-1000

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Abstract

A deterministic method of analyzing the relative criteria and safety conditions of nuclear power plants of various types has been developed. The method is based on comparing the provision of necessary safety functions with critical (minimum permissible) configurations of safety systems for accident management. On the basis of the developed method, the relative safety criteria and conditions of nuclear power plants with reactors of the VVER-1000 and AR-1000 type were determined in relation to the safety functions of the emergency refueling and cooling of the active zone of the reactor of tap generators. On the basis of the established relative criteria and safety conditions, the need for additional upgrades of the AR-1000 safety systems has been pre-determined to successfully ensure the safety functions of emergency refueling of the coolant/feed water and cooling of the active zone of the reactor and steam generators.

Keywords: safety, method of qualification of nuclear power plants.

Introduction

The lessons of the Fukushima accident determine the prospects for improving the safety of nuclear power plants (NPPs) of low power (modular reactors NuScale, SMR and others) and high power (AP-1000 WESTINGHOUSE), in which accident management is carried out by the circuits of natural circulation of passive safety systems (PSS). According to the results of the probabilistic safety analysis (PSA), the main probability indicator of nuclear safety (the frequency of damage to the active zone - CHPAZ) for such NPPs is of the order of 1/year, which corresponds to reactors with a high level of safety (3+). But operational experience and the lessons of major accidents determine the need to be "cautious" about the results of the primary accident event (PAE) in relation to the assessment of the level of safety of nuclear power plants, for example, for the following reasons:

1. In most cases, the probabilistic indicators of the PAE determining the initial emergency event are not sufficiently substantiated. In particular, the probability of the occurrence of an initial emergency event with a complete and long-term blackout of power units (analogous to the event at the Fukushima-Daiichi NPP) at the nuclear power plant with VVER-1000 was estimated to be of the order of 1/year, which determined the non-priority of such accidents (including in relation to the corresponding emergency measures). But after

the Fukushima accident, emergency events with complete and long-term blackout of power units became a priority for the entire global nuclear energy industry.

2. According to the results of the PAE, the CHPAZ of all power units of the Fukushima-Daiichi NPP met the established probability criteria; but severe accidents and destructive steam-gas explosions with catastrophic ecological consequences could not be prevented.

3. One of the main lessons of the Fukushima accident is the prioritization of relatively unlikely emergency events that have catastrophic environmental consequences.

For these and other reasons, deterministic methods of NPP safety analysis are a priority at the current stage of nuclear energy development.

In the presented work, a deterministic method of analysis of relative safety levels was developed using the example of VVER-100 and AR-1000 serial power units..

Analysis of literary sources

Numerical results of safety analysis by probabilistic and deterministic methods of NPP with VVER-1000, obtained by various calculation tools (codes) and users of codes, allow us to draw the following conclusions (for example, [1 - 14] and others:

1. Sufficiently substantiated critical (minimum permissible) configurations of safety systems, which ensure the successful performance of the necessary

safety functions for managing emergency processes in VVER-1000.

2. PSB VVER-1000 of the first generations of the safety level does not warn of the conditions of nuclear safety in terms of the maximum permissible temperature of the fuel cell shells during accidents and complete long-term blackout of power units.

For such accidents, the critical configuration is to supply the steam generator with a flow of feed water that corresponds to the nominal flow rate of one emergency electric feed pump (EMP).

The given results can be the basis for the development of a deterministic method of analyzing the relative safety levels of various types of nuclear power plants.

Deterministic method of analysis of relative conditions of NPP safety levels.

The deterministic method of analyzing the relative conditions of the safety level is based on the comparison of the critical (minimum) configurations of the safety systems (SB) of the VVER-1000/320 and AR-1000, which are necessary to ensure the safety functions of the reactor/steam generators (PG) fueling/cooling during accident management.

The composition of the SB VVER-1000/320 and AR-1000 for ensuring the safety functions of the reactor/gas reactor (FB) feeding/cooling is given in the table. 1.

Table 1.

The composition of the safety systems of the VVER-1000/320 and AR-1000 to ensure the safety functions of the reactor/gas reactor/gas supply (FB)

№	SB FB	
	VVER-1000/320	AR-1000
1	Three-channel active high-pressure boron emergency injection system (TQ 13): - nominal consumption in the 1st channel – 150 m ³ /h; - nominal back pressure – 11,0 MPa; - temperature at the entrance to the reactor – 20...60°C	Two-channel passive system of emergency refueling of the high-pressure natural circulation (PC) reactor (PSB-1)
2	Four-channel passive system of emergency reactor refueling/cooling (GO CAOZ)	Four-channel passive system of emergency feeding with boron solution of the reactor (PSB-2)
3	Three-channel active system of emergency and scheduled cooling of the low-pressure reactor (TQ 12): - nominal flow in the 1st channel – 800 m ³ /h; - nominal back pressure – 2.3 MPa; - the temperature at the entrance to the reactor in the emergency mode is 10...50°C	A single-channel passive system for the removal of final heat emissions (FC) through spent nuclear fuel storage pools (SNF) - PSB-3
4	Three-channel active system of emergency feeding of 4 PGs (TX): - nominal flow rate of the 1st channel – 150 m ³ /h; - nominal back pressure – 8.5...9.0 MPa; - the temperature at the entrance to the GHG is 10...50°C	Two-channel passive system of emergency power supply (PC) of 2 PGs through BV VYAP (PSB-4)

In the general case of initial emergency events, the critical (minimum) configurations of the SB FB VVER-1000/320:

$$1/3TQ13 + 2/4GESAO3 + 1/3TQ12 + 2/3TX \quad (1)$$

In the general case of initial emergency events, the critical configurations of the AR-1000 SB FB:

$$2/2PSB-1 + 4/4PSB-2 + 1/PSB-3 + 2/2PSB-4 \quad (2)$$

Given the identity of the power of the final heat releases of VVER-1000/320 and AR-1000, the relative conditions for ensuring nuclear safety:

$$G_{1A}(PSB-1) \geq G_{1W}(1/2TQ13) G_{1A}(PSB-1) \geq G_{1W}(1/3TQ13) \quad (3)$$

$$G_{1A}(PSB-2) \geq G_{2W}(2/4GOCAOZ) G_{2A}(PSB-1) \geq G_{1W}(2/4GOCAOZ) \quad (4)$$

$$G_{3A}(PSB-3) \geq G_{3W}(1/3TQ12) G_{3A}(PSB-3) \geq G_{3W}(1/3TQ12) \quad (5)$$

$$G_{4A}(PSB-4) \geq G_{4W}(2/3TX) G_{4A}(PSB-4) \geq G_{4W}(2/3TX) \quad (6)$$

$$i_{3A}(PSB-3) \geq i_{3W}(1/3TQ12) G_{3A}(PSB-3) \geq i_{3W}(1/3TQ12) \quad (7)$$

$$i_{4A}(PSB-4) \geq i_{4W}(2/3TX) i_{4A}(PSB-4) \geq i_{4W}(2/3TX) \quad (8)$$

where G - is the mass flow rate of the coolant in SB; i - is the specific enthalpy of the coolant/feed water at the entrance to the reactor/NG.

The equation of movement and heat balance of the coolant in the circuits of PC PSB:

$$\Delta\rho_1 \times q \times H_1 = \xi_1 \times G_{1A}^2 / (\rho \times F_1^2) \Delta\rho_1 \times q \times H_1 = \xi_1 \times G_{1A}^2 / (\rho \times F_1^2) \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta\rho_2 \times q \times H_2 = \xi_2 \times G_{2A}^2 / (\rho \times F_2^2) \Delta\rho_2 \times q \times H_2 = \xi_2 \times G_{2A}^2 / (\rho \times F_2^2) \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta\rho_3 \times q \times H_3 = \xi_3 \times G_{3A}^2 / (\rho \times F_3^2) \Delta\rho_3 \times q \times H_3 = \xi_3 \times G_{3A}^2 / (\rho \times F_3^2) \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta\rho_4 \times q \times H_4 = \xi_4 \times G_{4A}^2 / (\rho \times F_4^2) \Delta\rho_4 \times q \times H_4 = \xi_4 \times G_{4A}^2 / (\rho \times F_4^2) \quad (12)$$

$$G_{3A}(i_{OR} - i_{3A}) = R_T^{-1} \times A_T \times (T_{OR} - T_b) G_{3A}(i_{OR} - i_{3A}) = R_T^{-1} \times A_T \times (T_{OR} - T_b) \quad (13)$$

$$G_{4A}(i_{Oq} - i_{4A}) = R_T^{-1} \times A_T \times (T_{Oq} - T_b) G_{4A}(i_{Oq} - i_{4A}) = R_T^{-1} \times A_T \times (T_{Oq} - T_b) \quad (14)$$

where $\Delta\rho$ - is the difference in the densities of the heat carrier/gas feed water in the lowering and raising sections of the HP contours; q - acceleration of gravity; ξ - total parameter/coefficient of hydraulic resistance; F - the total cross-sectional area of the PSB pipelines; H - the height of the PSB contours; A_T - the total area of the heat exchange surface of the heat exchangers of the BVVNP; i_{OR}, T_{OR} - specific enthalpy and temperature of the coolant at the reactor outlet; i_{Oq}, T_{Oq} - specific enthalpy and temperature of

the feed water at the exit from the PG; R_T - the thermal resistance parameter of the heat exchange surface of the heat exchangers of BW SNP; T_b - the temperature in the WWTP; ρ - the maximum density of the coolant/feed water.

After transformations of equations (9)...(14) taking into account (3)...(8), the relative criteria and conditions for ensuring the nuclear safety of AR-1000:

$$K_1 = \frac{\Delta\rho \times q \times H_1 \times F_1^2 \times \rho}{\xi_1 \times G_{1W}^2} \geq 1 K_1 = \frac{\Delta\rho \times q \times H_1 \times F_1^2 \times \rho}{\xi_1 \times G_{1W}^2} \geq 1 \quad (15)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{\Delta\rho_2 \times q \times H_2 \times F_2^2 \times \rho}{\xi_2 \times G_{2W}^2} \geq 1 K_2 = \frac{\Delta\rho_2 \times q \times H_2 \times F_2^2 \times \rho}{\xi_2 \times G_{2W}^2} \geq 1 \quad (16)$$

$$K_3 = \frac{\Delta\rho_3 \times q \times H_3 \times F_3^2 \times \rho}{\xi_3 \times G_{3W}^2} \geq 1 K_3 = \frac{\Delta\rho_3 \times q \times H_3 \times F_3^2 \times \rho}{\xi_3 \times G_{3W}^2} \geq 1 \quad (17)$$

$$K_4 = \frac{\Delta\rho_4 \times q \times H_4 \times F_4^2 \times \rho}{\xi_4 \times G_{4W}^2} \geq 1 K_4 = \frac{\Delta\rho_4 \times q \times H_4 \times F_4^2 \times \rho}{\xi_4 \times G_{4W}^2} \geq 1 \quad (18)$$

$$K_5 = \frac{R_T^{-1} \times A_T \times (T_{OR} - T_b)}{G_{3W} \times (i_{OR} - i_{3W})} \geq 1 K_5 = \frac{R_T^{-1} \times A_T \times (T_{OR} - T_b)}{G_{3W} \times (i_{OR} - i_{3W})} \geq 1 \quad (19)$$

$$K_6 = \frac{R_T^{-1} \times A_T \times (T_{Oq} - T_b)}{G_{4W} \times (i_{Oq} - i_{4W})} \geq 1 K_6 = \frac{R_T^{-1} \times A_T \times (T_{Oq} - T_b)}{G_{4W} \times (i_{Oq} - i_{4W})} \geq 1 \quad (20)$$

Analysis of relative criteria and conditions for ensuring AR-1000 nuclear safety

Results and Discussion

Preliminary calculation estimates, taking into account the data in Table 1, of the obtained relative criteria and conditions for ensuring nuclear safety during accident management of the circuits of PSB AR-1000 (15)...(20) showed that the required height of the circuits of RSB-1, PSB-3, PSB- 4 should be several hundred meters. At lower values of the height of the contours of the PS RSB, in general, the necessary flow of heat carrier/feed water is provided for the successful execution of FB during accident management.

An alternative approach to improving the safety of emergency management of emergency services can be based on the use of emergency pumps with steam drives from natural gas. At relatively high pressures in the NG, such pumps can provide the necessary level of feed water in the NG during accidents, and, accordingly, provide the necessary conditions for cooling the active zone of the reactor.

But this issue needs a separate detailed consideration. In particular, similar emergency pumps with steam drives from boiling reactors were installed on power units at the Fukushima-Daiichi NPP; but could not prevent severe consequences of accidents in difficult conditions of extreme external influences. Therefore, "hard" requirements should be established for the justification of technical solutions for PSB emergency pumps with steam drives, taking into account the lessons of the Fukushima accident.

Conclusions

1. A deterministic method of analysis of relative criteria and safety conditions of nuclear power plants of various types has been developed. The method is based on comparing the provision of necessary safety functions with critical (minimum permissible) configurations of safety systems for accident management.

2. On the basis of the developed method, the relative safety criteria and conditions of nuclear power plants with reactors of the VVER-1000 and AR-1000 type were determined in relation to the safety functions of emergency refueling and cooling of the active zone of the reactor and steam generators.

3. On the basis of the established relative safety criteria and conditions, the need for additional modernizations of the AR-1000 safety systems has been predetermined for the successful provision of safety functions for emergency refueling of coolant/feed water and cooling of the active zone of the reactor and steam generators..

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest regarding this research, including financial, personal, authorship or other nature, which could be included in the research and its results presented in this article.

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